

MILESTONE 54: OVERVIEW UNITED4SURVEILLANCE (SCIENTIFIC) OUTPUT

UNITED FOR SURVEILLANCE IN EUROPE

JOIN THE MISSION TO BE BETTER PREPARED FOR FUTURE CROSS-BORDER HEALTH THREATS

Representing 24 countries in Europe, UNITED4Surveillance gathers expertise in public health, clinical microbiology, epidemiology and data-science to support the strengthening of integrated surveillance systems for infectious disease prevention and control on national and European level

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1. (Scientific) articles

1. Grøntvedt et al. Surveillance for Influenza A(H1N1)pdm09 in Swine and Humans in Norway. *In preparation*.
2. Jore S, Tonnessen R, Grøntvedt CA, Rydland K, Hauge AG, Hungnes O, Kristoffersen AB, Fossum E. A retrospective cross-sectional study (2009-2023): exploring influenza A(H1N1)pdm09 antibody time series in humans and swine and vaccine coverage in two target groups. *Zoonoses and Public Health*. 2026 March; 73:336-347. Available from: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/zph.70051>
3. Kerkvliet JJ, Stege PB, Coipan C, Lanzl M, van der Voort M, Mughini-Gras L, van der Weijden C, Kampfraath AA, Koene MGJ, van den Beld M, Pijnacker R, Franz E. Evaluation of routine One Health WGS-based surveillance of Salmonella Enteritidis and Typhimurium in the Netherlands. *Submitted Eurosurveillance*.
4. Larose T et al. Navigating force Majeure in EU4Health Projects: lessons from Norway's government reorganisation. *In preparation*.
5. Marbus SD, Boer TM, Veldhuijzen IK, van Gageldonk-Lafeber AB. Infectious disease surveillance in Dutch hospitals: what's in it for us? *BMC Health Services Research*. 2026 April; 26: 731. Available from: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s12913-026-14513-2>
6. Pijnacker R, van den Beld M, Ulrich A, Ceyskens PJ, van Cauteren D, Solveig Jore, Nielsen EM, Ethelberg S, Morabito S, Lanzl M, Franz E. Implementing whole genome sequencing for foodborne pathogen surveillance: insights and recommendations based on expert experiences. *Frontiers in Microbiology*. 2025 Dec; 16: 1-8. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/microbiology/articles/10.3389/fmicb.2025.1707621/abstract>
7. Sassu EL, Polzer D, Stätter M, Buzanich-Ladinig A, Klinger J, Leeb B, Wilhelm E, Cvjetkovic V, Schmoll f, Kpacka I, Revilla-Fernández S. Pilot multisectoral surveillance of swine influenza A virus in Austria reveals diverse lineages and potential human-to-swine H1N1pdm09 transmission. *In preparation*.
8. Torres-Ruesta A, Lehtonen T, Sane J, Leino T. Defining Severe Acute Respiratory Infection (SARI) hospitalisations in Finland: Evaluation of case definitions for register-based surveillance, 2021-2021. *In preparation*.
9. vom Felde genannt Imbush P et al. Collaborative development of open-source outbreak detection tools: Needs, concept and implementation. *Eur J Public Health*. 2024 Oct; 34: ckae144.1148. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/ckae144.1148>
10. vom Felde genannt Imbush P, Vietor AC, Markus I, Diercke M, Ullrich A. Automated outbreak detection systems in the EU: Requirements and challenges for its implementation, 2023-2024. *Under review JMIR Public Health Surveill*: Preprint available from: <https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.64898/2026.02.20.26346630v1.full>

2. (Poster) presentations

1. Galea N et al. Lessons learned : Building a Lab Based Gastrointestinal Surveillance System in Malta. Poster presented at: XI Malta Medical School Conference 2025; 4 Dec 2025; Valetta, Malta
2. Kairiene B et al. Presentation about UNITED4Surveillance and its activities during seminar INFODAY - information event to present the European Union Health Programme 2021-2027 "EU4HEALTH" (EU4HEALTH) and its Action Plan 2023; 11 April; Vilnius, Lithuania
3. Kairienė B. Fit for purpose surveillance – strategies to implement effective surveillance systems in EU/EEA countries under the new Serious Cross Border Health Threats Regulation (2022/2371). Conference presentation at: 16th European Public Health Conference; 10 Nov 2023; Dublin, Ireland
4. Kerkvliet JJ et al. Evaluation of routine One Health WGS-based surveillance of Salmonella Enteritidis and Typhimurium in the Netherlands. Poster presented at NVMM Scientific Spring Meeting; 30 March 2026; Arnhem, the Netherlands
5. Kerkvliet JJ et al. Evaluation of routine One Health WGS-based surveillance of Salmonella Enteritidis and Typhimurium in the Netherlands. Poster presented at: EOHA; 19 May 2026; Madrid.
6. Kerkvliet JJ et al. Evaluation of routine One Health WGS-based surveillance of Salmonella Enteritidis and Typhimurium in the Netherlands. Poster presented at: UNITED4Surveillance Closing Meeting; 20-21 May 2026; Utrecht, the Netherlands
7. Leino T et al. Development of Register-based surveillance of severe acute respiratory infection (SARI) hospitalizations in Finland. Poster submitted: ESCAIDE 2026.
8. Liptáková M et al. Project UNITED4Surveillance – Building Union and National capacities for integrated surveillance. Poster presented at: 31st Pečenka's Epidemiological Days; 11-13 Sept 2024; Plzeň, Czech Republic.
9. Marbus SD et al. Infectious disease surveillance in Dutch hospitals. Poster presented at UNITED4Surveillance Closing Meeting; 20-21 May 2026; Utrecht, the Netherlands
10. Masset H. Salmonella spp. as a be.Prepared case study for integration of health data as a way of strengthening preparedness for infectious diseases. Poster presented at: I3S conference, 23 June 2025; Saint-Malo, France
11. Melillo T et al. Strengthening Infectious disease Surveillance through Electronic Health Records and Automated Data Flows in Malta. Conference presentation at: 4th National Public Health Conference; 24-25 Nov 2023; Msida, Malta
12. Parys A. ZOOIS. Conference presentation at: 20205 SSID; 22 May; Brussels, Belgium
13. Sassu EL et al. Coordinated effort fort he surveillance of zoonotic influenza in Austria. Poster presented at: BeOH 2025; 22-23 Jan; Brussels, Belgium.
14. Sassu EL et al. Pilot multisectoral surveillance of swine influenza A virus in Austria reveals diverse lineages and potential human-to-swine H1N1pdm09 transmission. Poster submitted: ESFLU.
15. Sassu EL et al. Strengthening swine influenza surveillance in Austria through a multisectoral network: a pilot study from 2023-2025. Poster presented at: ESPHM 2026; 13-16 May, Florence, Italy.
16. Sassu EL et al. Strengthening swine influenza surveillance in Austria through a multisectoral network: a pilot study from 2023-2025. Poster presented at: UNITED4Surveillance Closing Meeting; 20-21 May 2026; Utrecht, the Netherlands
17. Sassu EL et al. Strengthening the communication between veterinary and medical authorities in the context of zoonotic influenza. Conference presentation at: OneH Congres 2026; 3-5 Jun; Saint-Quay-Portrieux; Brittany, France
18. Sciensano. ZOOIS: Zoonotische influenza surveillance bij varkensdierenartsen en varkens in België. Poster presented at: IPVS conference (International Pig Veterinary Society); 5 Dec 2025; Beveren, Belgium

19. Serdt M, Klepac P, Klavs I, Lejko Zupanc T, Logar M. UNITED4Surveillance – Union and national capacity building for integrated surveillance – Work package 3: hospital surveillance: surveillance of severe infectious diseases that lead to hospitalisation. Poster presented at: Slovenian National Conference on Public Health; 1-2 October 2024; Maribor, Slovenia.
20. SSI. "One Health - når mennesker og dyr smitter hinanden" (One Health – When Humans and Animals Infect Each Other), Presentation at: Nordic Infection Prevention and Control Conference; 14 April 2025; Gothenburg, Sweden
21. Stätter M. Main results of swine influenza surveillance in domestic pigs. Poster presented at: European Symposium of Porcine Health Management (ESPHM) 2025; 22 May; Bern, Switzerland
22. Van Dyck W. Major Salmonella Enteritidis outbreak linked to egg consumption. Conference presentation at: 2025 SSID; 22 May; Brussels, Belgium
23. Vietor AC. An open-source signal detection tool for infectious disease outbreaks: The development and application of signal detection methods within the European Public Health Community. Conference presentation at: DAGStat 2025 (German Working Group of Statistics); 24-28 April; Berlin, Germany.
24. Vietor AC. Collaborative development of a framework for automated signal detection for infectious disease outbreaks. Conference presentation at: 3rd (Inter-) National Conference on Infectious Disease Modeling 2025 (MONID); 26-28 Feb 2025; Berlin, Germany.
25. Vietor AC. Signal Detection Tool: An R shiny app supporting automated detection of infectious disease outbreaks. Conference presentation at: ShinyConf 2025; 9-11 April (online).
26. vom Felde genannt Imbush P et al. Collaborative development of open-source outbreak detection tools: Needs, concept and implementation. Poster presented at: 17th European Public Health Conference 2024; 12-15 Nov; Lisbon, Portugal.
27. WBVR. Poster presented at: Paradigm shifts for Global Oe Health; 24 April 2024; Wageningen, the Netherlands.
28. Witteveen-Freidl G et al. Lessons learnt form a One Health stakeholder analysis and systems mapping workshop on avian and swine influenza surveillance in humans in Denmark. Poster session presented at: ESCAIDE 2024; 20-22 Nov; Stockholm, Sweden.

3. Reports

1. WP2 - Task 1 report: [Legal challenges with respect to lab-data sharing in the EU/ EEA](#)
2. WP2 - Task 1: Pilot report - [Denmark](#)
3. WP2 - Task 1: Pilot report - [Finland](#)
4. WP2 - Task 1: Pilot report - [Norway](#)
5. WP2 - Task 1: Pilot report - [the Netherlands](#)
6. WP2 - Task 2: Evaluation report - [Denmark](#)
7. WP2 - Task 2: Evaluation report - [Finland](#)
8. WP2 - Task 2: Evaluation report - [Hungary](#)
9. WP2 - Task 2: Evaluation report - [Ireland](#)
10. WP2 - Task 2: Evaluation report - [Latvia](#)
11. WP2 - Task 2: Evaluation report - [Lithuania](#)
12. WP2 - Task 2: Evaluation report - [Malta](#)
13. WP2 - Task 2: Evaluation report - [the Netherlands](#)
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16. WP2 - Task 2: Evaluation report - [Slovenia](#)
17. WP3: Pilot report - [Finland](#)
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23. WP3: Pilot report - [Slovenia](#)
24. WP4: Pilot report - [Austria - E. tularensis](#)
25. WP4: Pilot report - [Austria - zoonotic influenza](#)
26. WP4: Pilot report - [Belgium - Salmonella](#)
27. WP4: Pilot report - [Belgium - zoonotic influenza](#)
28. WP4: Pilot report - [Denmark - STEC](#)
29. WP4: Pilot report - [Denmark - zoonotic influenza](#)
30. WP4: Pilot report - [Italy - Shiga toxin-producing E. coli \(STEC\)](#)
31. WP4: Pilot report - [Lithuania - Salmonella](#)
32. WP4: Pilot report - [Lithuania - Tick-borne Encephalitis \(TBE\)](#)
33. WP4: Pilot report - [the Netherlands - Salmonella & Campylobacter | UNITED4Surveillance](#)
34. WP4: Pilot report - [Spain - West Nile virus \(WNV\) | UNITED4Surveillance](#)

4. Deliverable reports

1. D1.1 Progress report
2. D1.2 Project booklet
3. D2.1 Review existing lab surveillance systems and outbreak detection systems
4. D2.2 Recommendations and trainings-package for improved lab-based reporting and outbreak detection
5. D3.1 Report on MS survey and piloting plans
6. D3.2 Recommendations and trainings-package for digitalized surveillance systems of severe infectious diseases
7. D4.1 Inventarisation goals, stakeholders and One Health surveillance systems
8. D4.2 Recommendations and trainings-package for implementing One Health surveillance
9. D5.1 Report on evaluation workshop
10. D5.2 Final evaluation report
11. D6.1 Project website
12. D6.2 UNITED4Surveillance infographic
13. D6.3 Initial assessment MS surveillance systems and needs assessment
14. D6.4 Final dissemination report
15. D7.1 Baseline report national sustainability plans
16. D7.2 Progress report on national sustainability plans implementation
17. D7.3 Final report: Roadmap to implementation of integration infectious diseases surveillance

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